

Animal Research Authorisation Procedures – Where Things Stand and What Needs to Change

Statement by the DFG's Permanent Senate
Commission on Animal Research

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1 Summary

In its statement¹ from 2018, the DFG's Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (SKTF) analysed problems arising in the authorisation procedures for animal experiments.

In order to obtain an overview of the current situation and of developments, the SKTF carried out a renewed assessment in 2023/2024, drawing on several sources of information:

1. a round-table discussion with animal welfare officers;
2. a round-table discussion with researchers;
3. a pilot study in which quantitative data on authorisation procedures was collected.²

While the situation in some federal states has improved in certain areas compared with 2018, a further impairment has been observed in most others. The **main points of criticism** are:

- ▶ the excessive bureaucracy involved in the procedures;
- ▶ legal uncertainties;
- ▶ heterogeneity in the interpretation of legal provisions and in procedural practice across the federal states;
- ▶ the lengthy duration of the proceedings.

According to researchers, the **negative impacts on the research system** already observed in 2018 have become more pronounced:

- ▶ hindrance to scientific progress and biomedical advances due to delays in research projects;
- ▶ reduced international competitiveness of Germany as a research location and unequal conditions within Germany;
- ▶ disadvantages for researchers in early stages of their career or in fixed-term positions, who are particularly affected by lengthy and unpredictable processing times.

¹ DFG, Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2018): [Genehmigungsverfahren für Tierversuche – Stellungnahme](#) (German only).

² DFG, Valeska M. Stephan and the Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2025): Pilot Study on the Practice of Animal Research Authorisation Procedures in Germany – A Critical Analysis, [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17177712](#).

Scientific progress in biological and biomedical research is indispensable to safeguarding public health. At the same time, research is a driving force behind medical progress and prosperity in Germany. **In order to fulfil their societal mission while at the same time upholding their particular responsibility in the use of animals for research, scientists need reliable framework conditions.** Authorisation procedures need to be realigned so as to combine the highest standards of animal welfare in experimental research with the promotion of innovation and competitiveness within the research system. **With this in mind, the SKTF calls on the competent ministries and authorities at both federal and state level to implement the following measures:**

- ▶ ensure an appropriate depth of assessment by the authorities that respects the subject-specific expertise of researchers;
- ▶ reduce the bureaucratic workload and administrative hurdles where these do not contribute to improving animal welfare;
- ▶ establish legal certainty through national harmonisation of authorisation procedures, with a clear and uniform definition of key process stages;
- ▶ adhere strictly to the statutory processing deadlines;
- ▶ regularly monitor authorisation procedures based on quantitative data.

2 Background

Animal experiments are an indispensable part of the methodological spectrum in many areas of the life sciences. They play a crucial role in improving our understanding of vital functions and diseases, and in advancing medical progress. This research provides the foundation for safeguarding the well-being of society and for ensuring progress, innovation and prosperity.

Animal research is strictly regulated. At European level, the legal framework is set out in Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. Nationally, animal experiments in Germany are governed by the Animal Welfare Act (*Tierschutzgesetz*, TierSchG) and the Animal Welfare Laboratory Animal Regulation (*Tierschutzversuchstierverordnung*, TierSchVersV), which go beyond the provisions of the EU Directive in several respects.

A key guiding principle for the responsible conduct of animal experiments is the 3Rs principle (Replace, Reduce, Refine): animal experiments may only be carried out if no alternative suitable methods are available to answer the scientific question; the number of animals used and the severity of procedures must be limited to what is strictly necessary. Consistent implementation of the 3Rs principle is an intrinsic interest for high quality research and is fully supported³ ⁴by the DFG, not least because animal welfare and the validity of research results are inextricably linked and mutually dependent.

Every animal experiment requires authorisation (Section 8 (1)(1) TierSchG). The authorisation procedures ensure that each research project complies with legal requirements and with the principles of the 3Rs, thus serving an essential function in upholding animal welfare as a constitutional objective (Article 20a Basic Law, *Grundgesetz*). At the same time, research involving animals that cannot be replaced by non-animal methods must not be unnecessarily restricted or hindered by administrative procedures.

In its 2018 statement, the SKTF identified numerous problems in the practical implementation of the authorisation procedures that had a serious negative impact on research projects. Following the 2021 amendments to the Animal Welfare Act which also affected the authorisation

³ DFG, Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2019): [Animal Experimentation in Research: The 3Rs Principle and the Validity of Scientific Research – Guidelines](#).

⁴ DFG, Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2022): Thesenpapier zur Sicherung leistungsfähiger biomedizinischer Forschung unter Wahrung höchster Tierschutzstandards, [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6956898](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6956898).

procedures, the SKTF undertook a renewed and systematic assessment of the current situation in 2023/2024. The findings of this assessment are presented and discussed below.

3 Current situation

3.1 Insights gained from the round-table discussions

In order to obtain a comprehensive picture of perceptions of the current situation regarding authorisation procedures across Germany, the SKTF conducted two round-table discussions. The first, held in May 2023, brought together 15 animal welfare officers from 13 federal states; the second, held in October 2023, involved 17 researchers from 11 federal states.

The outcomes of these discussions show that participants regard procedural practice as having generally deteriorated since 2018. Discrepancies between federal states became apparent during the discussions. The situation regarding authorisation procedures and relations with the authorities was considered to be good in only one state. In most states or administrative regions, the situation was described as poor or very poor. Participants from all represented states reported a **steady increase** – in some cases **an outright escalation** – in **bureaucratic workload**, in particular:

- ▶ a marked increase in the level of detail required in application documents;
- ▶ an increasing depth of assessment by the authorities;
- ▶ an increase in the number of queries raised by the authorities;
- ▶ additional notification requirements in the case of amendments.

This increase in bureaucracy cannot be attributed to specific considerations aimed at improving animal welfare. The amendment of the TierSchG appears to have further reinforced these developments. In some federal states, where the right of associations to bring legal action (*Verbandsklagerecht*) is implemented, it was also cited as a factor contributing to the increase in procedural detail and depth of assessment. In addition to the rise in the administrative workload, new procedures have been introduced such as an authorisation requirement with regard to animal experiments conducted for the purposes of training or continuing education (under Section 36 TierSchVersV); previously, only a simplified authorisation process (“notification”) was required in such cases.

The recent round-table discussions also indicate that **major problems identified in the past remain widespread**, particularly:

- ▶ legal uncertainties in the interpretation of the regulations;
- ▶ lack of nationwide harmonisation of procedures;
- ▶ long duration of the authorisation procedures.

In some federal states, positive changes have been noted in terms of shorter processing times. Where this is the case, the acceleration of procedures is attributed either to an increased number of personnel in the competent authorities or else to legal action taken by applicants. Some participants also highlighted constructive and positive communication with local authorities based on long-standing and trusting relationships. However, many also reported a general atmosphere of mistrust on the part of authorities towards researchers, thereby hindering open and cooperative interaction.

Across the board, participants of the round-table discussions criticised the fact that the preparation and processing of authorisation applications ties up considerable resources, diverting time and capacity away from research itself. This particularly affects smaller research groups such as those involving researchers at an early stage of their career, since such groups lack funding to employ additional administrative staff.

All in all, the discussions paint a **worrying picture of the current situation** in Germany. Many participants expressed increasing frustration, saying that the situation had steadily worsened, the level of scrutiny had become absurd, and that biomedical research was at a crossroads. The situation in Germany is also increasingly perceived as problematic internationally. There are increasing reports of researchers:

- ▶ being reluctant to engage in animal research due to the high workload, lengthy procedures and the lack of clear legal and procedural frameworks;
- ▶ declining offers of professorships or the establishment of new research groups (under prestigious funding programmes such as ERC grants or junior research groups, for instance);
- ▶ avoiding certain locations and relocating projects within Germany or from Germany to other countries;

- ▶ opting not to conduct animal experiments at all, even when such experiments are essential to the scientific validity of their research (this point applies particularly among early-career researchers).

Under the current framework conditions, it is becoming increasingly difficult for researchers in Germany to remain internationally competitive in key areas of the life sciences. For the sake of both animal welfare and the advancement of scientific and medical progress, **a change in the mindset of how authorisation procedures are handled is urgently needed** – one that ensures **uniform animal welfare standards, prevents the relocation of animal experiments to countries with lower standards, and strengthens the performance and innovative capacity of the research system**. Concrete recommendations are presented in Section 4.

3.2 Pilot study with quantitative data

In 2023/2024, the SKTF conducted a survey to complement the qualitative assessment of authorisation procedures gathered through the round-table discussions and trace the specific stages of the procedural workflow based on quantitative data. The results of this survey are published in a pilot study⁵ released simultaneously with this statement. The survey involved the collection of key data on a total of 468 individual authorisation procedures across 14 federal states from animal welfare officers or the corresponding institutional bodies at university and non-university research institutions.

The data collected in the pilot study do not allow for a systematically comparative, statistically robust analysis of administrative processes across the entire country, as the number of cases varies between federal states and procedural workflows differ in some instances. However, the study does provide the first comprehensive dataset allowing key trends and challenges to be identified in connection with authorisation procedures for animal experiments in academic research in Germany, as well as data relating to individual process stages.

The pilot study identifies three main **areas of concern** which – with varying degrees of intensity depending on the federal state – result in **delays, a substantial administrative workload and a lack of planning reliability** for researchers:

⁵ DFG, Valeska M. Stephan and the Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2025): Pilot Study on the Practice of Animal Research Authorisation Procedures in Germany – A Critical Analysis, [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17177712](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17177712).

1) Duration of authorisation procedures

Section 32 (1) TierSchVersV, in accordance with Article 41(1) of Directive 2010/63/EU, stipulates that applications for animal experiments must be processed by the competent authority within 40 working days, extendable once by up to 15 working days in duly justified cases. Looking at the net processing time taken by an authority (i.e. the time between confirmation of completeness of the application (Section 32(3) TierSchVersV) and the authority's decision excluding the time applicants take to respond to queries) the pilot study analysis indicates a median of 35 working days (mean: 38.3 working days). Considering the full range of the distribution, it becomes apparent that the 40-day deadline is exceeded in 39.5 per cent of cases. In 14 per cent of cases, the net processing time exceeded 55 days.

Notably, it was not possible to determine this time span in 53 per cent of all submitted datasets because **no date for confirmation of completeness was provided**. These cases indicate that the procedural practice of the competent authorities concerned does not include confirmation of completeness: it is therefore not possible to determine how long the procedure lasts. **This means that procedural documentation obligations arising from the time limits as stipulated by law are effectively neglected.**

In terms of researchers' practical work, the formal procedural stages set out by law are less relevant than the total duration of the procedure – from the date of submission of the authorisation application through to the date of the final decision. This overall duration has a median of 56.5 net working days (mean: 69.1 net working days, or approximately two-and-a-half to three calendar months). Taking into account the total duration without deducting query rounds, the median increases to 85 working days (mean: 98 working days, or approximately four to five calendar months). **Given that most research projects are designed to last three to four years, such lengthy authorisation procedures result in considerable delays in project implementation and constitute a substantial disadvantage in a competitive research environment. This particularly affects researchers in early career phases whose fixed-term contracts are often tied directly to research projects.** Doctoral projects funded through third-party grants cannot commence, placing researchers under considerable pressure at a stage of their careers that is already highly demanding.

In addition, processing times vary considerably between federal states. This can put researchers at specific locations at a marked disadvantage, running counter to the objective of the EU Directive to harmonise the framework conditions for animal research across Europe.

2) Volume of queries

As an indicator of the level of detail in the authorisation process, the pilot study recorded the number of queries raised by the competent authorities. On average, each authorisation application generated 19 queries (median: 13) across two query rounds. Although there is generally a **high volume of queries**, the actual number varies greatly. For a significant number of applications, the number of queries was considerably higher – around 10 per cent of applications involved 40 or more queries. **Marked differences were also evident between authorities**, with the number of queries being significantly higher in some federal states than in others. It is not possible to identify potential causes of these discrepancies by analysing the data collected in the pilot study. However, it does seem likely that the differences are not due to variations in the quality of the applications between federal states but rather to the differing procedural practices of the competent authorities. It is also possible that the right of associations to bring legal action (*Verbandsklagerecht*) contributes to an increased number of queries; this applies in certain federal states.

3) Differences in procedure between the competent authorities

Across **all dimensions of analysis – processing times, number of queries and formal procedural stages** – the pilot study clearly highlights one central finding: the **considerable differences between federal states**. Both the average duration of procedures and the number of queries vary substantially. There are also differences in key procedural stages, such as the mode of submission, the issuing of the confirmation of receipt or the calculation of fees. A particularly critical issue concerns the confirmation of completeness in accordance with Section 32(3) TierSchVersV. The data collected indicates that the point at which an application is considered “complete” is interpreted very differently. In most cases, formal completeness applies, but in some cases substantive completeness is required, or else other criteria are applied. Several authorities include consultation with the animal experiments commission (in accordance with Section 15 TierSchG) when determining completeness, while some authorities issue no formal confirmation of completeness at all, making it impossible to verify compliance with the 40-day deadline.

The results of the pilot study **underline the urgent need for greater harmonisation of the authorisation procedures**. One essential aspect here is the unambiguous definition of “completeness” and the point at which the confirmation of receipt is issued.

3.3 Additional framework conditions

In addition to the difficulties identified through the round-table discussions and the pilot study, researchers are faced with **further overarching challenges that have a major impact on their day-to-day scientific work**. Particularly concerning is the **legal uncertainty surrounding the interpretation of a “reasonable cause”** (*vernünftiger Grund*, Section 1 TierSchG) for the killing of animals bred for scientific purposes but not used for their intended research aims. This means that even when acting in full compliance with the most rigorous animal welfare standards, researchers and animal facility staff still risk criminal prosecution for carrying out their professional duties.

Furthermore, in recent years, it has increasingly been observed that, during **severity assessments** conducted by authorities, even long-established experimental procedures are being assigned higher severity classifications, without objective or scientifically substantiated criteria or studies to support this change.

Finally, there has been a sharp **decline in the number of laboratory animals** used since 2019. While to some extent this trend undoubtedly reflects the success of measures implemented in line with the 3Rs principle, **there is concern that this may also be attributable to the discontinuation or relocation of scientifically significant research approaches based on animal models**. Such developments are problematic not only in that they **weaken the innovative capacity and competitiveness of the research system in Germany**, but also – and perhaps most importantly – because they risk a **loss of national sovereignty over animal welfare standards and, potentially, a reduction in the level of protection afforded to laboratory animals**.

4 Recommendations

Taking into account the round-table discussions with animal welfare officers and researchers, as well as the pilot study on the practice of authorisation procedures, it emerges that the situation is now perceived as having deteriorated in most respects compared with the findings of the 2018 SKTF statement. Major problems relating to authorisation procedures have persisted for a long time and run counter to the central objectives of the 2021 amendment to TierSchG.⁶ Increasingly, the **procedural practice of the authorisation process** is perceived as a **serious impediment to researchers' work**. The **strength and competitiveness of Germany as a research location** in biology and biomedicine are at risk of suffering lasting damage, **as are the prospects for early-career researchers**.

The SKTF believes that the procedures must be reformed. **Authorisation procedures should be organised and implemented in such a way that they adequately reflect Germany's high animal welfare standards while at the same time fostering and supporting the innovative capacity of the research system**. Reliable and supportive conditions for research are essential in the international competition to attract the best researchers.⁷

With regard to the authorisation procedures for animal experiments, there is a need for reform in two areas in particular:

1) The practice of administrative authorisation

The **main problems** in terms of procedural practice are **excessive bureaucracy**, the steadily increasing **level of detail and documentation required in the authorisation procedures**, **unclear and inconsistent procedural workflows**, and the **long duration of the procedures**.

⁶ BT-Drs 19/27629, Begründung des Gesetzentwurfs, [Explanatory Memorandum to the Draft Bill], p. 17.

⁷ Similar conclusions are arrived at in publications such as [Nationale Strategie für Gen- und zellbasierte Therapie](#) [National Strategy for Gene- and Cell-Based Therapy] (June 2024), (p. 88 f.), and [Gutachten der Expertenkommission Forschung und Innovation \(EFI\)](#) [Report of the Commission of Experts for Research and Innovation (EFI)] issued in 2021.

The SKTF specifically recommends the following:

- ▶ **The depth of review should be adapted** to “the degree of detail appropriate to the nature of the experimental project” (*die Detailliertheit, die der Art des Versuchsvorhabens angemessen ist*; Section 8 (1)(3) TierSchG). **The review process should respect the subject-specific expertise of researchers.** Any bureaucratic effort and administrative hurdles that do not contribute to improving animal welfare should be strictly avoided. In view of limited staff capacity within the competent authorities, the growing level of detail required in application documents and the increasing depth of review must be curtailed as a matter of urgency.
- ▶ The administrative **workload caused by queries should be reduced** by
 - focusing on queries that relate directly to specific questions of animal welfare, and
 - consolidating written queries and requests for clarification into a single procedural stage.
- ▶ Clear criteria should be developed so that the **concept of “completeness”** (Section 32 (3) TierSchVersV) is defined as meaning the formal **completeness of the application documents**. Completeness should be confirmed to applicants, and the statutory processing period should begin on the date of confirmation.
- ▶ **The procedure for issuing confirmations of receipt** (Section 32 (2) TierSchVersV) **should be standardised**. The confirmation of receipt should be issued immediately and not be delayed until requested by the applicant or until a formal assessment has been carried out.
- ▶ The above recommendations are to contribute to **accelerating the procedures**. All in all, the authorisation process should be structured in such a way as to ensure **strict compliance with the statutory processing deadlines**.
- ▶ **Successfully approved research grant proposals** that have undergone extensive quality assurance (e.g. DFG, ERC, BMBF) should be recognised by the authorising authorities as clear **evidence of the scientific relevance of the project**.
- ▶ The **digitalisation of procedural workflows** should be further advanced, in particular through:

- the consistent **introduction of digital submission** routes;
- the **electronic documentation of ongoing authorisations** (ideally also in English) so as to ensure transparency and facilitate the traceability of amendments (Article 38 (4) Directive 2010/63/EU).

First proposed by the SKTF in its 2018 statement and already implemented in similar form in several federal states, there is a model **best-practice workflow** (see Figure 1) which combines the key aspects of the recommendations relating to authorisation procedures.

Figure 1: Model workflow for the authorisation procedure

2) Nationwide harmonisation at federal level

Both the round-table discussions and the pilot study clearly demonstrate the **problems arising from the lack of harmonisation of procedures**. These are evident in procedural workflows, in the interpretation and implementation of individual process stages, and in processing times. The **discrepancies in procedural practice** between individual authorities and across federal states **can give rise to considerable disadvantages for researchers at certain locations**, even meaning that research activities could **potentially be relocated outside Germany**. The lack of harmonisation in implementing legal provisions also contradicts the core aim of Directive 2010/63/EU to establish uniform conditions for animal research across Europe.

The SKTF specifically recommends the following:

- ▶ The establishment of a separate law governing scientific animal experiments, as agreed in the Federal Government's coalition agreement, should be taken as an opportunity to eliminate **existing legal uncertainties and procedural problems, and to reduce excessive bureaucracy**. The law should reaffirm Germany's commitment to high animal welfare standards while at the same time strengthening the innovative capacity, efficiency and competitiveness of life sciences research in Germany.
- ▶ In the short term, a **revision of the General Administrative Regulation** (*Allgemeine Verwaltungsvorschrift*, AVV) is required as a matter of urgency. Through the AVV, it is possible to establish legal certainty in relation to indeterminate legal concepts and provide authorities with uniform, binding administrative guidance under Article 84 (2) of the Basic Law (*Grundgesetz*, GG) for the implementation of statutory provisions. It can make a key contribution to achieving a uniform approach to key stages of the authorisation procedure. The AVV has not been updated for 24 years, however, and has lost much of its relevance in light of repeated amendments to animal welfare legislation. It should therefore be adapted to the current legal framework as a matter of urgency. The aspects of procedural practice mentioned under 1 should be taken into account in this revision.
- ▶ In order to harmonise authorisation procedures and standardise the content and level of detail in the assessment procedures, **application documentation requirements should be standardised nationwide** and supplemented with additional tools such as completion guides or checklists.
- ▶ **Regular exchange between researchers, animal welfare officers and authorities** on procedural and factual matters should be promoted (e.g. through regular dialogue

between research organisations and the responsible working group for animal welfare of the LAV, the umbrella body for consumer protection).

- ▶ **Monitoring of the authorisation procedures**, as carried out in the accompanying pilot study, should take place on a regular basis to track developments and further optimise processes.

The scientific community needs reliable framework conditions in order to fulfil its societal mission while at the same time upholding its particular responsibility in the use of animals for research. With this in mind, the SKTF is calling on the competent ministries and authorities at both federal and state level to take the necessary measures to accelerate and harmonise authorisation procedures, reduce bureaucratic requirements and eliminate legal uncertainties. The effective implementation of procedural practice requires a concerted effort on the part of all those concerned and close dialogue between researchers, animal welfare officers, authorities and ministries with the aim of jointly upholding the dual objectives of maintaining the highest standards of animal welfare and enabling the research system in Germany to achieve its full innovative potential.

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